

IN THE MIDST OF A VISIONAL INFINITE MOTION— ENCOUNTER BETWEEN THE RED/GREEN OF KLEE'S *FUGUE IN RED* AND THE RED/GREEN OF BOULEZ'S *CONSTELLATION-MIROIR OF 3RD PIANO SONATA*

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SUMMARY

Klee added six works to his handwritten oeuvre catalogue, including *Fugue in Red*, which originated from an experiment on the movement between the complementary colours of red and green in 1921.* This reminded me of the *Constellation* in Boulez's unfinished *3rd Piano Sonata*, which was printed in red and green. In the process of making the imperceptible (the invisible or the inaudible) perceptible, I found a surprising similarity in the methods of organization used by both artists. Furthermore, I will describe how the "grey" or "intermediate

areas" located between the complementary colours in Klee's work find their acoustic correspondence in Boulez's work, drawing on my experience as a pianist. I will also consider the implications of the circular structure that the two artists used to overcome the linear time structure. Finally, I will touch on several interesting examples of these structures that the violinist Klee discovered in Bach's works, and I will try to shed light on the mystery of Klee, who in his works explored the theme of "infinite movement."

*See Kersten 2005, p. 172; Keller 2024.

INTRODUCTION

The words are really at quite a remove from the essential mystery; tone and colour in themselves are the mystery. What a fascinating fate it is to master painting today (as it once was to master music).¹ While brilliantly expressing the infinite process of creating works of art in words, Klee went on to create "polyphonic paintings" that transcended multiple artistic fields. Pierre Boulez, a composer, conductor, pianist, and critic who excelled at "creative analysis," was deeply moved by Klee's work, and often drew on it as a new "concept of time" in his own musical creations. Consequently, there are concepts that are similar to each other as well as techniques and words that

are almost the same between Boulez and Klee. This is because such concepts are not only used as a way of manipulating "colour" and "sound," but also as "appearances" at a sophisticated structural level with correspondences between the visual field and the world of sound. In this article, I will examine the creative thinking of Klee and Boulez in parallel, focusing on the common conceptual foundations of the following distinctive concepts expressed in Klee's works: "polarities between complementary colours," "diagonals," "intermediate areas," "shapeless base layer,"² "circular movements," and "polyphony (simultaneity)."

Abb. 1
Paul Klee, *Fuge in Rot* [*Fugue in Red*], 1921, 69, watercolour and pencil on paper on cardboard, 24.4 x 31.5 cm, private collection, Switzerland, on extended loan to the Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image

Abb. 2
Paul Klee, *Reifendes Wachstum* [*Ripening Growth*], 1921, 71, watercolour and pencil on paper, top and bottom paper strips, on cardboard, 41.9 x 23.8 cm, location unknown
Image credits: Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Archive

Abb. 3
Paul Klee, "Contributions to the theory of pictorial form," pen, pencil and watercolour on paper, 20.2 x 16.3 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, PKS BF/162
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

"... IF [...] THE TIME ELEMENT COULD BE OVERCOME BY A RETROGRADE MOTION THAT WOULD PENETRATE CONSCIOUSNESS ..."³

Klee painted in 1921 a series of watercolours using the complementary colours of red and green: *Red-Green City*, 1921, 67; *Pottery*, 1921, 68; *Fugue in Red*, 1921, 69 (FIG. 1); *Hanging Fruit*, 1921, 70; *Ripening Growth*, 1921, 71 (FIG. 2); and *Portrait of a Lady's Smile*, 1921, 72.⁴ In particular, in *Fugue in Red*, which Boulez often referred to, one might have the initial impression that the tones change from left to right, and from darkness to light. However, as Wolfgang Kersten points out,⁵ once you have an understanding of Klee's watercolour technique, it becomes doubtful whether the work can be viewed in a uni-directional way. Klee's watercolours are composed of thin, transparent layers that are layered on top of each other—from bright red to dark red, and from bright to dark green, and finally black—creating gradations of colour between complementary hues. This is also discussed analytically in Klee's lectures on colour theory at the Bauhaus in Weimar, based on the idea of "glazing"⁶ (FIG. 3). The above six works by Klee represent the

various results of his experiments based upon these ideas. The direction of Klee's creative process is exactly the opposite of the initial visual impression. The body of the work that is being created moves not from left to right as one might initially believe, but from right to left, that is, from light to dark, and from front to back in terms of colour tone. Additionally, let us also recall Klee's statement here: "The orientation of the space of the work is based on the mirror image of the work to itself."⁷ Therefore, rather than asking which direction this 'fugue' is moving in, it is better to think of the two extremes of red/green and light/dark as being related to each other—"Motion and counter-mo-

tion of the pendulum result in equilibration of movement."⁸ In the same way, just as the direction of the arrows in Klee's pendulum is indefinite due to the unknown element of time, so too is the directionality of the colour fugue indefinite, thus there is an unlimited ambiguity at work here. This is why we can experience the "motion" that breathes within Klee's paintings in a richer way. As is clear from the final entry in Klee's sketchbook, this is the path to "the spectral colour circle where all the arrows are superfluous."⁹ From the perspective we have discussed above, I think that Klee, as well as those

Abb. 4
 Pierre Boulez, "Troisième sonate pour piano—formant 3—Constellation-Miroir," pp. a-b: Mélange, Points 3, Blocs II
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with an understanding of music, will surely think of Bach's retrograde/mirror image canon.¹⁰ In fact, a sort of imitation of this type of canon is used in hidden form in Boulez's music.¹¹ The *Constellation-Miroir* of the third movement of Boulez's *3rd Sonata*, which is the main focus of this article, has the flexibility to be performed in the opposite direction, as the title suggests. In particular, the *Fugue in Red* has been compared to music because the musical term "fugue" is included in the title, but as Boulez says, since the musical fugue itself has a fairly strict structure, we should be careful not to hastily link the artwork to music based on its title.¹² However, the way in which the waves of form and colour successively overlap on the canvas is certainly a way in which the "score that can be heard."¹³ From this viewpoint, the harmony of colour changes in the vertical direction and can be likened to one voice fading away while a new voice enters. In the process of Klee "making visible the content of a simple thing," he did not limit himself to merely realizing this concept by painting a visual abstraction of a "fugue," but rather, *Fugue in Red* can be said to be

an essential and important springboard to the "structuring" of his theme of "a movement based upon the polarity of complementary colours." Neither Boulez nor Klee studied structure for the sake of structure. Boulez's approach to his work seems to be the same as that of Klee. Boulez's structuring was not about measuring time in music, but about "expanding perception, that is, as a means for making the normally imperceptible forces more resonant and thereby more visible."¹⁴ Influenced by the content of Klee's lecture notes, Boulez also explored how to appeal to human perception within a relative worldview.¹⁵

WHAT IS BROUGHT ABOUT BY THE MOVEMENT OF POLARITY BETWEEN RED AND GREEN?

Since I have been able to appreciate the works in Klee's series of red and green watercolours, and especially Klee's *Fugue in Red*, in this new way, I have been viewing the large-scale colourful sheet music of the third movement *Constellation* (FIG. 4) of Boulez's *3rd Sonata* as an extension of the five human senses. This is a representative work of "Chance controlled," a

famous response work by Boulez to John Cage's proposal of the concept of "Chance Music."¹⁶ Conventional musical forms have a linear, one-way time axis that progresses from one point to another, but in Boulez's *Constellation*, the path is a network and the performer follows the arrows before and after each section, as if they were strolling through a city map and choosing their own path. Therefore, the work is a movable system that allows you to choose a route that is continually being updated in a finite world. This unconventional and unprecedented layout of the musical score has a lot of white space, and the fragments of the musical phrases seem to be floating on the pages. This was inspired by Stéphane Mallarmé's *Un coup de dés jamais n'abolira le hasard* (*A Throw of the Dice will Never Abolish Chance*), 1897, which Boulez was fascinated by.¹⁷ This poem by Mallarmé has a layout that suggests that there are many variations in the connections between words. Narrative is avoided, and it is thought that these rearrangements are more important than the linear development of a single thought. This reminds us of the concept of "constellation," which was important for understanding the art of the 20th century, including the "Constellations" series created by Arp around 1930.¹⁸ In fact, it is not confirmed that Klee used the concept of "constellation" in the titles of his works or in his writings.¹⁹

However, Fujio Maeda has taken the rather unusual stance of focusing on a passage from Grohmann's review of some of the works made after the 1930s,²⁰ which are generally referred to as "constructive," including Klee's *Schwebendes*, 1930, 222, which says, "... but the absence of a fixed point of reference turns the whole into a constellation."²¹ In addition, Maeda proposes that the act of shaping, which is a process of continuously transforming and overcoming the shape and

form of the work that has been created, is nothing other than the Goethean concept of "metamorphosis" as an essential formative opportunity.²² In this article, I have already speculated that a non-unidirectional concept of time exists in Klee's 1921 work *Fugue in Red* which depicts the layering of forms, and this can be read as implying that the signs of the "constellation" concept of form that emerged around 1930 can be found in Klee's work of 1921.²³ This score by Boulez is printed in the complementary colours of red and green, but I am not trying to link it to *Fugue in Red* just because of that. As Boulez says, "the language of sight is different from the language of hearing, and the principles of acoustics are by no means the same as the principles of colour."²⁴ Nevertheless, I would like to quote another of Boulez's statements here—"For a musician, it is important that the musician understands that the constructions Klee creates in the visual world can be transferred into the world of sounds, given the fact that there is a constructive idea of an interrelation."²⁵ So, I would like to consider whether this piece can be seen as one realization of Klee's "movement between the polarities green and red."

First, the green colour in this score symbolizes the set titled "Points," and the red colour symbolizes the set titled "Blocs." These partial titles (Points and Blocs) typify the "structural forms" used here. Points are based on single frequencies that are isolated and separate, and chords only occur when two or several points overlap simultaneously. The Blocs are based on constantly changing "clusters of sound" that appear "vertically" or are broken down "horizontally" into rapid sequences.²⁶ They are repeated alternately as they develop. As we can see, just as Klee depicted "polar movements between complementary colours" as "hierarchies of form," Boulez gave musical

Abb. 5
Paul Klee, "Theory of pictorial configuration: I.4 Structure," pencil and coloured pencil on paper, 28.8 x 22.3 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, PKS BG I/04/096 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

structures to the red and the green, which are at opposite ends of the spectrum, respectively. The way in which Boulez juxtaposes such contrasting structures is a characteristic of his music. He relativizes and actualizes space and time.

BOULEZ'S "STRIATED TIME" / "SMOOTH TIME" AND KLEE'S "DIVIDUAL" / "INDIVIDUAL"

When it comes to Boulez's method of contrasting expression, his famous explanation of the contrasting structures of "Striated Time" and "Smooth Time," which he presented at the Darmstadt International Summer Courses for New Music in 1960, is well known.²⁷ If you know how Boulez differentiates between these

that goes beyond rhythm"²⁹ seems to have been the inspiration for Boulez's "striated space"/"smooth space." This classification by Klee was carefully categorized and given various conceptual definitions to avoid falling into formalism and to "unify diverse things into one."³⁰ These structures are expressed through analysis of their relative properties, and their structures are clearly defined. Boulez finds a "contrast" between the 'clearly defined form' of the foreground and the 'unclear form' of the background³¹ that exists in Klee's works. This involves two levels of perception.³² Boulez took this idea of contrast from Klee and applied it to the concept of time,³³ developing his own music through the alternation of contrasts, as in the *Points and Blocs* of the *3rd Sonata*. This is one of his most representative expressions. It is also evident in his later works such as *Sur Incise*, 1996/1998, for ensembles, the expanded version of *Incises*, 2001, for piano, and *Messagesquise*, 1976–1977, for a cello ensemble,³⁴ where the contrasting sections with their slow, flexible rhythms and rapid, unending motion alternate with each other. In the time element of his works, you can always find events with clear contrasts like this.³⁵

Abb. 6
Pierre Boulez, "Troisième sonate pour piano—formant 3—Constellation-Miroir," p. e: Points 2, Blocs I © Copyright 1963 by Universal Edition (London) Ltd., London, UE 13293 b LW

two structures, you may be reminded of the items in Klee's composition, "dividual" and "individual" (FIG. 5).²⁸ Klee's concept of "dividual"/"individual" and "having a rhythmic cycle = rhythm"/"composition

Returning to the *3rd Sonata*, there are three "green = Points" and two "red = Blocs"³⁶ (FIG. 6) alternating with each other. The performers alternately experience the "extreme acoustic structures" of green and red and simultaneously follows the "movement between complementary colours" with their eyes, performing while slipping through a maze-like web. This visual experience is only experienced by the performers themselves during the performance. However, the listener will hear the two clearly different structural forms going back and forth. We are in a kind of dreamlike process of "individualization" through the shifting between the two structural forms that Boulez

presents. It is like looking at a work by Klee. The reason it is dreamlike is that there is no fixed “one-way” order from here to there, but rather the relationships are loosely connected, so there is a certain fixedness but also a sense of mobility. Those who come into contact with this work will be involved in the creative act on an ongoing basis.³⁷

Let’s now delve a little deeper into the above-mentioned dreamlike process. We have been referring to “polar movements” through such contrasts, but we must not forget that Klee often depicted “middle movements” between active and passive forms. The same can be said of Boulez. He often hints at the “diagonal” or “intermediate area”³⁸ between two contrasting structures, and in a letter to his colleague the composer Stockhausen, Boulez himself mentions that “one can read the vertical, horizontal and diagonal lines [in *Constellation*].”³⁹ This “diagonal line” can also be expressed by replacing it with the idea of “grey” in the stationary domain,⁴⁰ which is similar to the center of a swinging scale and exists in the middle of the red/green colour scale mentioned in Klee’s lecture on colour. As we will examine in the next chapter, this leads to the “amorphous ground”⁴¹, so named by Boulez because he was greatly influenced by Klee’s paintings, which have a multi-layered structure within the picture plane. Here, I will attempt to see if we can find a common conceptual foundation between Boulez and Klee. It is a realm that is neither polyphony nor homophony, neither Point nor Block, neither vertical nor horizontal, rather, it is the catalyst for “these two tendencies gradually permeating each other and creating a kind of free style.”⁴²

The key to this is the “diagonal line” system. In fact, in addition to the Points and Blocs, there is a microcosmic section at the beginning of the constellation called “Mélange” which means “mixture”

of the two structures [Furthermore, here the colours are reversed, with the Blocs being green and the Points being red].⁴³ This work uses a basic 12-tone row⁴⁴ as a common underlying theme, not only for the Points and Blocs, but also for the entire huge *3rd Sonata*, and 48 variations are derived from this.⁴⁵ Boulez essentially manipulates this 12-tone row not in a linear fashion, but by dividing it into groups of one, two or three tones.⁴⁶ This is a work with a perfect serial structure, in which all 48 types of variations are used to the full, not only in terms of pitch but also in terms of other elements such as such as tessitura and duration, attack, through methods such as intensification, grouping, transposition, and division.⁴⁷ There is no room in this article to go into the structure in detail, but in the research on this by the musicologist and pianist Peter O’Hagan, there are occasional references to similarities with Klee’s theory of form,⁴⁸ suggesting that this topic may also be of interest to Klee researchers. In particular, I would like to focus on the Boulez method, which is a method of creating complex structures and clusters of sounds by selecting two of the 48 types of 12-tone row series mentioned above and multiplying them using mathematical systems such as crossover techniques and chord multiplication.⁴⁹ This method of Boulez’s can be said to be a “diagonal” usage. The linear traces of the original theme are completely permeated and cannot be seen here. This is accomplished by manipulating the “intermediate area” that is imperceptible.

THE ACOUSTIC INTERMEDIATE AREA IN BOULEZ’S CONSTELLATION = “AMORPHOUS GROUND”

Let’s take a closer look at the “diagonal line” and “intermediate area” mentioned above and consider how they are acoustically realized in the *3rd Sonata: Constella-*

tion. In this work in particular, Boulez brilliantly realized the “gray”⁵⁰ or “amorphous ground” of Klee as an effect of “sustained sound,” which attempts to resist the function of the piano, whose sound is destined to decay as soon as it is played.

Technically speaking, if you press a key on the piano without producing a sound in a certain range (with only the dampers of those keys separated from the strings) and then play another note on the same key, the sustained sound will reverberate in the background like a “ghost.” This phenomenon is an acoustic phenomenon that does not occur unless the key is pressed with a certain degree of force.⁵¹

This kind of undercurrent resonance is also used effectively in later works by Boulez, such as his masterpiece *Structure II* for two pianos (1956), and his later solo piano works *Incise*, 2001 (FIG. 7) (an expanded version of a shorter version of the same piece from 1994), and *Une page d'éphéméride*, 2005.⁵² As Boulez says, a simple transposition between painting and music would only result in a banal case, so it was necessary to create something “that could be compared to the transubstantiation in the sacrament of the Eucharist” in the way that Klee had achieved.⁵³

Boulez places the harmonics technique (the effect of “amorphous ground”) in both the Points and Blocs of *Constella-*

tion and allows the effects to “penetrate” each other. Through Boulez’s intellectual magical technique, the various “amorphous ground,” as indicated on the score, can be either large or small, and this acoustic space becomes a shining, “controlled” polyhedron. The pianist cannot afford to let their guard down for a moment. For this reason, the composer not only uses harmonics, but also uses a “limited” technique combining subtle use of the pedal with staccato or tenuto attacks,⁵⁴ to make the pianist explicitly explore the nature of the “amorphous ground” with their ears and whole body. The player, always with his whole body and soul, differentiates space and time through Boulez’s complex method of ordering, and the red of the Blocs and the green of the Points are transformed into energy precisely by the act of playing. In Blocs, explosive masses of sound, mainly in the extremely low registers, are occasionally heard, then broken up into “horizontals” in powerful and rapid succession, while harmonic sequences in the extremely high registers create a shimmering galaxy of sound worlds, contributing to a dynamic and resonant acoustic field in a wide range of registers.

In Points, the limited range of notes, the slight swings in the slow tempo, the isolated sounds and simple curves floating irregularly on the thin surface, delicately make one aware of a “smooth time-space,” as if time had stopped.⁵⁵ In this way, in every dimension, we accumulate a diagonally intersecting experience of Blocs and Points. The piano itself becomes a huge, delicate resonator that never stops moving, even for a moment. In *Constellation*, the ability to respond to such acrobatic, sustained, multilayered acoustic events is required not only of the performer but also of the listener.⁵⁶

Is this kind of perceptual experience suggested by Boulez, in which the viewer’s perception is “shaken” and “con-

Abb. 7
Pierre Boulez, “Incises pour piano [version 2001],” p. 15, bottom part (with sostenuto pedal)
© Copyright 1994, 2004 by Universal Edition
A. G., Wien, UE 31966

Abb. 8
Paul Klee, *Garten Vision* [*Garden Vision*], 1925, 196, oil on cardboard mounted on wooden strainer, 24 × 30 cm, Artizon Museum, Ishibashi Foundation, Tokyo
© Artizon Museum, Ishibashi Foundation, Tokyo

trolled” when confronted with a work that has multiple layers, such as “signs,” “webs,” and “ambiguous backgrounds,” not unlike perceptual experience in Klee’s *Vision of a Garden* (FIG. 8)?⁵⁷ In this way, we are able to contemplate their works, which express a whole “world” being fragmented and unified, through our own perceptions.

KLEE AND BOULEZ ORDERED “MOTION”

The *3rd Sonata* by Boulez was an unfinished work called “work in progress.”⁵⁸ Boulez had a passion for creating a huge “expanded world” made up of five pieces, but in the end, he was unable to realize his vision in this world. Therefore, *Constellation* is a piece that was completed as part of his overall vision. In his 1959 Darmstadt presentation of the overall plan for the *3rd Sonata*, his sonata was composed of five “formants” instead of the conventional “thematicism”⁵⁹: 1. *Antiphonie*, 2. *Trope*⁶⁰, 3. *Constellation-Miroir*, 4. *Strophe*, 5. *Séquence*. This structure is based on a mobile, symmetrical arrangement with *Constellation* [*Constellation-Miroir*] at its core (FIG. 9). From this dia-

gram, you can see how the arrangement is achieved. In other words, the four formants, which are grouped in twos around the central nucleus (which is itself a group of cells), rotate on two concentric orbits. The outer orbit can become the inner orbit, and vice versa. “The possibilities for performance given by the above are limited to eight in total due to the symmetry that permutations and transpositions must follow,” (FIG. 9) he explains.⁶¹ However, the only scores that have been published in their current, completed form are the monochrome printing of the second formant, *Trope*⁶², and the red/green printing of the third formant, *Constellation*, which is at the center of Boulez’s overall conception. After the composer’s death, fragments of the first formant’s colourless *Antiphonie* were published in 2019. It is a piece that can be performed with a documentary spirit, and one that allows us to recognize the embryonic state of the music.⁶³

In a letter to Stockhausen in September 1957, before the Darmstadt premiere, Boulez often spoke privately about the overall conception of the *3rd Sonata*. Boulez’s informal view is that the “idea of colour” described below, together with his “idea of a form that moves symmetrically,” can be considered in accordance with the thinking of Klee. Boulez’s works often have the intention of destroying “one-way” forms, and Boulez was concerned with how written works and performances could escape from a “rigid state.” Here too, he uses “unconscious memory” and “latent relationships” to create a complex web, distancing us from simple linear thinking.⁶⁴ This evokes the “colour solid of Klee.”⁶⁵ And this is how Klee and Boulez ordered “motion.”⁶⁶ The following is Boulez’s colour scheme as described in the letter:

Abb. 9
Pierre Boulez, "Troisième sonate pour piano—formant 1—Antiphonie," p. XIX: Original plan, "Place des formants" scheme based on the original sketch by Sylvano Bussotti, in: "Zu meiner III. Sonate [original edition]," transl. from French by Heinz Klaus Metzger, printed in: *Darmstädter Beiträge zur Neuen Musik*, vol. III, Mainz: B. Schott's Söhne, 1960, pp. 27–40
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"All of this is in different colours, in order to indicate how one must play.
Antiphonie: violet
Trope: blue-black
Constellation: red and green
Strophe: black
Séquence: blue"⁶⁷

Abb. 10
Paul Klee, "Theory of pictorial configuration: I.2 Principal Order," coloured pencil, pencil and pen on paper, 27.5 x 20.7 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, PKS BG I/02/156
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

The colours violet, blue, red, green and black above seem to reflect partly Klee's "colour solid" (FIG. 10).⁶⁸ Here again, I am tempted to speculate. The red/green used in *Constellation* to represent the complementary colours between their diameters are also connected on the circumference, which represents a gradation. And on the same Klee colour circle (on the semicircle), there are also violet and blue. As a further dimension, the vertical line that penetrates this colour circle represents light = white and dark = black at each end. In Boulez's draft, there is only black, which means only the one extreme of darkness. Boulez's colour idea for *3rd Sonata* only represents half of Klee's colour solid. It is worth considering why Boulez chose only these colours. In his blueprint, we cannot see any other complementary colours. It seems implicitly to suggest the existence of an invisible counterpart, and with this

he seems to have already announced the sense of a "work in progress" in advance.

In the end, most of Boulez's colour-coded ideas were not realized due to his death. This speculation of mine about the colours may be nothing more than a coincidence. However, the fact that Boulez conceived of this *3rd Sonata* as a work that emerged from "a pronounced predilection for large 'assemblages' focused on a series of limited possibilities"⁶⁹ and that the five formants were structurally connected is very reminiscent of Mallarmé's cosmology in *Un Coup de Dés Jamais N'abolira le Hasard*.⁷⁰ This is why I was compelled to recall here the suggestive "colour solid" diagrams of Klee, which also referred to a "large assemblage" that had organized the motion of colour in a structural way.

Furthermore, instead of the conventional "pieces," Boulez deliberately adopted the term "formant," an analogy to acoustics, for the five pieces that make up this *3rd Sonata*. "A particular timbre is characterized by the formants of a specific frequency range that give it its distinctive timbre. The emergence of each piece results from structural formants, that is, general characteristics that can give rise to various developments. Each formant appears only in the various 'de-

velopments' that can be constructed by (musical) substitution, superimposition, interaction, and destruction."⁷¹ In a letter to Stockhausen before the official announcement, Boulez also explained that "the form develops in a hazy band between constant identical bands."⁷² If we look at this explanation in its essence, it reminds us of the various results of the experiments with motion between the complementary colours of red and green by Klee, which I mentioned at the beginning of this article, namely, his series of six watercolours painted in 1921. Therefore, in a metaphorical sense, we could say that the "[all] five formants" of Boulez's *3rd Sonata* are the six different "developments" or "formants" of the form and colour created by Klee.

A PROVISIONAL SUMMARY OF THE DISCUSSION THUS FAR

So far, we have been considering the composition and penetration of the order of "motion" in time and space, from the movement between the complementary colours of red and green to the overall harmony of the "colour solid," while comparing Klee's plastic thinking and Boulez's musical thinking. To begin with, it is important to note that the foundation of Klee's thinking about form is based on thorough research into the monochromatic (monochrome) realm of "lines" that express scale, and "light and dark" that express weight, until "colour" is ordered and "motion" is achieved. In this sense, if we view the movement between the complementary colours of red and green as a means within the larger framework of the movement between the two extremes of static/dynamic or chaos/cosmos,⁷³ we may be able to perceive Klee's paintings in a more musical way. From here, we will also touch on the lively issues of "perspective" and "horizontal/vertical" that involve the psychological and physical experiences that underpin Klee's theory of

colour. The two musical cases mentioned below, in which Klee was engaged with Bach through his performances as a violinist, are episodes based on the "score" of music that is, fittingly, monochromatic (black and white).

"...HERE, THE TIME ELEMENT BECOMES A SPATIAL ELEMENT."⁷⁴

I was fortunate enough to see the well-worn score of the J. S. Bach *Sonata for Violin and Harpsichord* that Klee and his wife Lily frequently performed at the archive in the Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, last year (June 2024). Among the Bach pieces, I found traces of their annotations on the score of the fourth movement of *No. 3 BWV 1016*.⁷⁵ This piece is in three parts, and the first part is a theme with a sound pattern that resembles a fine zigzag wave of neighbour tones of 16th notes,⁷⁶ but the middle section changes completely, with the rhythm of triplets dominating and the tune changing to a gentle, curving elegance. What is more, on the triplets of Lily's piano part here, the rewriting of the groupings is written in red and blue quite clearly. In other words, the 123, 123 grouping of three notes in each triplet is replaced by a different articulation of 231, 231, with each note shifted by one, and the effect is that the zigzag figure in the first part is more exposed than in the elegance of the second part (FIG. 11).⁷⁷ Following this notation makes the performance more difficult, but I actually tried performing this interesting idea as a duo with a violin, and I greatly empathized with my partner as I experienced the thrilling "sense of time transcending and the overlapping unity" created by the difference in rhythm between the first and second parts.⁷⁸ Suddenly, I recalled the words from Klee's diary. "My awareness has again deepened by repeatedly playing Bach. Never yet have I experienced Bach with such intensity, never yet felt so at one

Abb. 11
 Johann Sebastian Bach, *Sechs Sonaten für
 Pianoforte und Violine*, Leipzig: C. F. Peters, p.
 46, Sonate III, Allegro, Zentrum Paul Klee,
 Bern, SFK Mu PK gN 2.3
 © Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

with him.”⁷⁹ This was Klee’s realisation during his time in Gersthofen away from Lily,⁸⁰ but it is also possible that Klee may have rewritten the piano score when he and his wife were playing together after returning home, with this feeling in his heart.

In a sense, this is a little like the method that Boulez sensed in Debussy’s *La Mer*.⁸¹ In Debussy’s music, when he expresses waves, we encounter melodic phrases with more detailed note patterns using 16th notes and 32nd notes, and melodic phrases with somewhat slower triplets,⁸² but Boulez says that “these two types of melodic phrase are spatial, as well as temporal, because they are auditory or acoustic objects in space, and they overlap with each other.”⁸³ Even if they don’t actually overlap, I think Boulez is also talking about the kind of spatiotem-

poral simultaneity that occurs in listening, where two time axes overlap and are perceived as superimposed on each other in memory and in time. This reminds me of the words from Klee’s diary, “Yesterday and tomorrow as simultaneous [...] the time element becomes a spatial element.”⁸⁴ Boulez himself says that he was able to draw out such inferences infinitely in his musical works thanks to Klee’s lectures on “perspective.”⁸⁵

THE SUBDIVISION AND DEEPENING OF SPACE-TIME

As another example, I would like to cite a case of Klee’s “formative thinking” that is directly linked to Bach’s musical notation. Here, the expression of “weight” as an order of “light and dark” and the expression of the contrasting nature of “horizontal” and “vertical” are used. Through a comparison of the musical and the pictorial, we can read the differentiation and deepening of space-time. The most appropriate example of this is “a pictorial representation using J. S. Bach’s three-voice movement score”⁸⁶ (FIG. 12). This is an interesting experiment by Klee, who analysed the “structure” of music as if looking at it through a microscope. The work by J. S. Bach that Klee used here is the fourth movement of the sixth *Sonata for Violin and Harpsichord* mentioned above, which is a three-voice score. Klee used grey and black to express the weight of the strong and weak beats in the layers of the beat.⁸⁷ As a comparison to this musical reality, I would also like to mention a contemporary piano piece by the Japanese contemporary composer Takeo Hoshiya⁸⁸ called *Four Seasons for piano*⁸⁹ (FIG. 13), which has a similar appearance to Klee’s graphic score piece. I performed it at my piano recital in 2024.⁹⁰ I chose it for its visual qualities, but the composer himself was unaware of Klee’s experiments. Hoshiya uses white, grey, and black not as layers of rhythm, but as the

Abb. 12
Paul Klee, "Contributions to the theory of pictorial form," leaflet, pen on paper, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, PKS BF/054
Klee's pictorial expression based on the example of the score of J. S. Bach's three-voice movement.
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

expression of dynamics that Klee omitted.⁹¹ (Unusually for contemporary music, this piece maintains a triple time throughout, rather than changing time signatures.)

What I want to convey here is that I experienced Klee's thinking about form through performance of the score for *Four*

"weight" and "tension-relaxation" (FIG. 14). Klee treats the vertical and horizontal dimensions as "rhythms of the most primitive structure in which the diagonal line disappears, and the problem of equilibrium is eliminated."⁹³ During the performance, there is a sharp exchange between these two primitive structures. To borrow an expression from Klee, "the person falling down and lying unconscious becomes the Baustein"—i. e. the vertical dimension."⁹⁴ In other words, "the base expands, and with it the horizontal line expands at the expense of the vertical line. A remarkable relaxation, or epic tempo, arises in contrast to the dramatic qualities of the vertical character."⁹⁵ The above can be observed in Klee's paintings, such as *Monument of the Fertile Country*, 1929, 41 (FIG. 15). Will Grohmann and Ole Henrik Moe observed this painting by Klee as a musical analogy, in which horizontal layers are cut by vertical and diagonal lines, and rhythmic and mobile motives are introduced as differences in "various tones." Boulez takes such an analysis as being right on the mark.⁹⁶

Here, we can see that the visual and formative elements were intended to affect the audience and the performers as physical and psychological things. I have interpreted this contemporary music under the guidance of Klee's formative

Abb. 13
Takeo Hoshiya, The score of *Four Seasons for Piano*, p. 8, ed. by Takeo Hoshiya
© Kayou-Sha Co. LTD, Tokyo JAPAN, 2017

Seasons for Piano. There is a contrast here between the rectangular boxes that represent long notes and the vertical black lines that represent extremely short notes.⁹² As the diagram shows, the painterly expression of size and length conveys the dynamics and values of the notes directly to the performer as visual

Abb. 14
Takeo Hoshiya, The score of *Four Seasons for Piano*, p. 8, ed. by Takeo Hoshiya
© Kayou-Sha Co. LTD, Tokyo JAPAN, 2017

thinking. Klee's "diagonal movement that tries to achieve balance"⁹⁷ is felt in music through the sense of sound in time. This resulted in a "pictorial score." As Boulez says, if it "is based on a more solid correspondence,"⁹⁸ and if it is ultimately deeply connected to the actual experience of performance, then we will find a certain

later years, and the fact that his works have a true musicality with a sense of "movement" to them.

Like most music scores, Klee's monochrome rendition of "Formative Expression from Bach" seems to be the result of a fairly dispassionate extraction process with a keen eye for observation. This spirit of Klee inspired composers like Boulez in particular. Like Klee, he tried to fundamentally rethink the conventional concepts of time and space in music and create something completely new by creatively breaking down stereotypes and preconceived notions of reality. The differentiated structures that were supposed to be opposites were eventually absorbed into "background resonance" forever cast into an unfinished world. In the process of analysing Boulez's "painting scores" while referring to Klee's *Das bildnerische Denken*, I realized that there is a historical background that resonates like a basso continuo between the two. Boulez premiered his *Piano Sonata No. 3* at the Darmstadt Summer Courses for New Music in September 1957, and as he recalled in the late 1980s, Stockhausen, who was also participating in the Darmstadt courses, gave Boulez a copy of Klee's *Das bildnerische Denken*, which had been published in 1956. "About thirty years ago, Stockhausen gave me *Das bildnerische Denken*, the book that contains Klee's Bauhaus lessons. While presenting it, he expressly remarked, and drummed into me: 'You will see that Klee is the best composition teacher of all.' I thought his enthusiasm went a little too far; in my view I had already received some good composition lessons, and I had already composed works like *Le marteau sans maître*. Since I could not yet read German, I studied the examples in the text in order to reconstruct its logic by myself, which was not always easy to do. The more I explored these lessons, the more I became aware that Stockhausen was completely

Abb. 15
Paul Klee, *Monument im Fruchland* [*Monument in the Fertile Country*], 1929, 41, watercolour and pencil on paper on cardboard, 45.7 x 30.8 cm, Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern
© Zentrum Paul Klee, Bern, Image Archive

parallel relationship in the various organizational structures. I can't help but feel that there is an essential connection between the fact that Klee continued to play the violin privately until he fell ill in his

right. Hardly any of the examples I was unravelling were related to music. Most of the time they had nothing to do with it, but in all instances, I could nevertheless make connections with my own work. From then on, I became more and more attached to Klee. Texts on the creative process by a creative genius of such stature, and in such acute wordings, are very rare.”⁹⁹

As we have already seen, the final part of Klee’s *Das bildnerische Denken* contains the painter’s theory of colour and also includes a black and white illustration of *Fugue in Red*. Boulez may have seen the original of this painting at the Klee exhibition held at the Kunst- und Museumsverein Wuppertal and Kunsthalle Hamburg in 1956. Then, in 1960, the first colour illustration of the painting was published in the book *Klee. Etude biographique et critique* by Nello Ponente, published by Skira in Geneva, and the painting became famous even in French-speaking countries. In any case, the historical research into the relationship between the music of Boulez and the paintings of Klee, which transcends the genres of music and painting, will be a subject for interdisciplinary research in the future.

As a pianist, my own task is to embody and deepen the world created by the rare exchange and interaction between composers and painters, and my “Klee Piano Recitals,” which I have been holding for about 10 years,¹⁰⁰ is a project that seeks to explore and experience together with the audience unexpected sonic scenes that arise “in the midst of a dreamlike infinite movement,” resonances which form in the “encounter” between musical works by Boulez, Bach, and Japanese composers, etc., and Klee’s pictorial creations.¹⁰¹

¹ Klee 1964, p. 393, no. 1121.

² See Boulez 2015, p. 87, “ce fond amorphe.” Boulez calls it the “informal background” in English, see Boulez 1994, in chapter 8, “The Painting of Klee.”

³ Klee 1964, p. 374, no. 1081, “If, in music, the time element could be overcome by a retrograde motion that would penetrate consciousness, then a renaissance might still be thinkable.”

⁴ See Keller 2024, Abb. 2 “Paul Klee, Œuvre-Katalog 1918–1926, 1921, 59–79 [S. 112–113]” and see Kersten 2005, pp. 171–172.

⁵ Kersten 2005, p. 163, “Dem ersten visuellen Reiz folgend, mag es naheliegen anzunehmen, im Bild erfolge eine Bewegung von dunkel nach hell, von links nach rechts und von hinten nach vorne; tatsächlich verhält es sich in Berücksichtigung der Aquarelltechnik jeweils genau umgekehrt.”

⁶ See Spiller 1961, p. 474, “In the language of painting this way of mixing colours is called glazing. Separate coats are laid on at intervals. At each step something is added: from left to right less and less, from right to left more and more. The result, or rather the sum, remains the same. By the gradation of our coats we obtain a precisely graduated movement from red to green-red to green, or the other way round.” Cf. Klee BF/163: “Diese Art des Farbmischens wird in der Malersprache lasieren genannt. Sie ist ein addieren von zeitlich getrennten Posten. Es kommt mit jedem Stadium etwas hinzu. Von links nach rechts immer etwas weniger hinzu, von rechts nach links immer etwas mehr. Das Resultat oder besser, die Summe bleibt dieselbe. Durch die Stufung im Summieren erhalten wir im Endeffekt eine präzis gestufte Bewegung von ganz rot zu grünrot zu grün oder umgekehrt.”

⁷ Klee BG I.1/10, “die Orientierung im Raume des Werkes vollzieht sich auf Grund der Vorstellung dass das Werk das Spiegelbild zum Ich selbst, und zwar aufrechtes Spiegelbild zu einem stehenden Ich, oder zum mindesten zu einem aufrechten Ich.”

⁸ Klee 1953, p. 53, IV.34.

⁹ Ibid., p. 61, IV.43, “We have arrived at the spectral colour circle where all the arrows are superfluous. Because the question is no longer:

‘to move there’ but to be ‘everywhere’ and consequently also ‘There!’”

- ¹⁰ Here, I dare to make a connection to Klee, and the first thing that comes to mind is the score of “6-voice triple canon BWV1076” that J. S. Bach has in his hand in his famous portrait. In fact, this is a work J. S. Bach submitted to join the Music Academic Correspondence Association, whose president was the translator of the German edition of J. J. Fux’s music theory book *Gradus ad Parnassum*.
- ¹¹ There are clearly retrograde forms in Boulez’s piano works, especially in the 12 Notations and the second movements of his *Piano Sonatas No. 1* and No. 2. For clear examples of his unique use of canon imitation (crab canon), see e. g. O’Hagan 2017, p. 45 (No. 11 of the Twelve Notations), and for the use of hidden canon imitation (crab canon), see *ibid.*, p. 256 (“Structure II”). See also my performance of Boulez’s *Sonata No. 2*, <https://youtu.be/u-96ve0DPP8?si=GrkJFS06AwIG-vCm> (last accessed 6th of April, 2025). This fourth movement ends with the Bach cipher.
- ¹² Boulez 2015, p. 73.
- ¹³ Kersten 2005, p. 162, note 38: “malerische Partitur.”
- ¹⁴ Deleuze 1986, p. 100, “Ce que veut dire élargir la perception, c’est rendre sensibles, sonores (ou visibles) des forces ordinairement imperceptibles.”
- ¹⁵ See Klee BF/153–154, etc., and Boulez 1987, pp. 98–99, 125, 127, 138, etc.
- ¹⁶ Boulez 2019, see Preface p. XXV, “[...] And everything is justified in extremely controlled chance. I’m working intensively on all this at the moment in order to find a structurally aleatoric form, combined with fixed forms. I think I’m on the right road. But what destructions on the way [...] that’s to say that their movement became a succession of fixations. This may explain to you clearly (or almost clearly ...) what I’m wanting to get at [...]. Without forgetting Mallarmé (but willingly forgetting poor, brave Cage!).” Some quotations from Boulez’s letter to Karlheinz Stockhausen, 27 September 1957, after the premiere of the Third Sonata at Darmstadt on 25 September 1957, and before its repeat in Berlin

on 28 September 1957 (Paul Sacher Foundation, Karlheinz Stockhausen Collection).

- ¹⁷ Boulez 1981, pp. 151–163, chapter “Sonate ‘que me veux-tu’ (Troisième sonate).”
- ¹⁸ Maeda 2012, pp. 103–140, chapter “Modeling as a constellation Klee and H. Arp in 1930.”
- ¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 120.
- ²⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 103.
- ²¹ Grohmann 1954, p. 273, “... das Fehlen eines festen Beziehungspunktes aber lässt aus dem Ganzen eine Konstellation werden.”
- ²² Maeda, p. 137.
- ²³ Maeda 2012, pp. 103–140, chapter “Modeling as a constellation Klee and H. Arp in 1930.”
- ²⁴ Boulez 1989, pp. 51, “Le langage de la vue diffère de celui de l’oreille, les principes acoustiques ne sont pas du tout les mêmes que ceux de la couleur.”
- ²⁵ Boulez 2015, p. 78.
- ²⁶ Boulez 1981, pp. 159–160, chapter “Sonate ‘que me veux-tu’ (Troisième sonate).”
- ²⁷ See the above note 16, and Boulez 1987, especially see diagram pp. 98–99, and in detail pp. 35–113.
- ²⁸ Klee BG I.4/96, BG I.4/272, etc.
- ²⁹ See the above note 15.
- ³⁰ Klee BF/153–154.
- ³¹ See Boulez 1994, in chapter 8 “The Painting of Klee.”
- ³² *Ibid.*
- ³³ See *ibid.* Here, Boulez took this idea of contrast from Klee and applied it in his *Eclat*.
- ³⁴ These works are dedicated to the late conductor Paul Sacher by Boulez. *Messagequise* is a cello solo and 6 cello piece dedicated to Sacher’s 70th birthday, <https://youtu.be/Cfnf15xVb8c?si=zL018nwCAJEPb7CL> (last accessed 6th of April, 2025). *Sur Incises* (1996–1998) dedicated to Sacher’s 90th birthday, for three pianos, three harps and three percussion instruments, is a remake and expanded version of the short piano solo piece *Incises* (1994), which was written for the piano competition, Concorso Umberto Micheli. See *Sur Incises* on youtube, <https://youtu.be/HCQI6Wu3QxE?si=0LGA9QjJKpnAVt-R> (last accessed 6th of April, 2025). The name “Sacher” is used as a musical name embedded in these

works. The creative history of *Incises* by Boulez is a very good example of “work in progress.” After writing *Sur incises*, Boulez wrote an expanded version, *Incises* (2001) as a piano piece, <https://youtu.be/fL0oLXGIYZs?si=uTnsDqBz166v9RHC> (last accessed 6th of April, 2025). The piece was inspired by his earlier piece for piano, *Incises* (1994). In the Lent section, Boulez used a lot of background resonance with the sustain pedal. There are flexible sections, but on the other hand, the *Vif* section is a pulse section. These two contrasting sections appear alternately, and in his later years, this style becomes clear. This seems to be an expression of Boulez’s attitude of trying to contribute to a clearer way of listening to contemporary music, in which the listener discovers the form by instinctively perceiving certain musical gestures. Cf. O’Hagan 2021, Boulez 1994.

³⁵ O’Hagan 2021, pp. 46, 65; and O’Hagan 2017, pp. 317–318.

³⁶ See the above note 21.

³⁷ Boulez 2019, “To offset such compositional renunciation, one must have recourse to a new concept of development which would be essentially discontinuous, but in a way that is both foreseeable and foreseen.” See also the note 16.

³⁸ Deleuze 1986, pp. 98–99, “Chaque fois la diagonale est comme un vecteur-bloc d’harmonie et de mélodie, une fonction de temporalisation. Et la composition musicale de la Recherche, selon Proust, apparaît de cette façon: des blocs dedurée toujours changeants, à vitesse variable et altération libre, sur une diagonale qui fait la seule unité de l’œuvre, la transversale de toutes les parties. L’unité du voyage ne sera ni dans les vues verticales du paysage, qui sont comme des coupes harmoniques, ni dans la ligne mélodique du parcours, mais dans la diagonale, ‘d’une fenêtre à l’autre,’ qui permet de fondre en un bloc de transformation ou de durée la succession des points vus et le mouvement du point de vues.”

³⁹ O’Hagan 2017, p. 282, note 5, “Mais voilà à peu près ce que je pense: [...] Formant 3 Constellation Forme On peut lire vertical, horizontal diagonal [...].” Quoted after Boulez’s letter to Stockhausen, around September 28, 1957, Stockhausen Stiftung.

⁴⁰ Spiller 1961, p. 475, Klee BF/164.

⁴¹ See the above note 2.

⁴² Boulez 1981, p. 288, “Au fur et à mesure que la musique évolua, ces deux tendances se sont interpénétrées de plus en plus pour donner naissance à une espèce de style libre, avec de nombreux degrés de variation entre l’homophonie pure et la polyphonie pure.” See *ibid.*, pp. 286–295 and see Deleuze 1986, pp. 98–100.

⁴³ On the “Mélange of Constellation,” see O’Hagan 2017, pp. 222–225.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 192, see the musical illustration of Example 7.1, Third Sonata, basic series, “*Je-f-h-f#-g#-g-hb-c-a-d-c#-eb.*” A note on the 12-tone row (series): This is a series of 12 semitones within an octave, devised and systematized by Schoenberg and others in the early 1920s in order to break free from the constraints of tonality, in which each of these tones is used once. First, this is called the original form, and four other forms are created: the retrograde form (following the original form backwards), the inverse form (reversing the order of the intervals), and the inverse-retrograde form (a combination of the inverse and retrograde forms). Then, by combining these with transposed forms in which the starting note is moved to each of the 12 notes, 48 sequences are created, and the music composed on this basis is called 12-tone music. Boulez then extended this method to include not only pitch but also duration, dynamics, attack, timbre, etc.

⁴⁵ O’Hagan 2017, p. 217, see the musical illustration of Example 7.17.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 216 “[...] the first stage of the process is the series itself, with the sixfold division of the twelve notes of the series into segments consisting of 1-3-3-2-1-2 groups.” Also see Example 7.17, and Table 7.9 of pp. 217.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 185–240.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, and on O’Hagan’s mention of similarity with Klee’s pictorial theory, see *ibid.*, pp. 218–220.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, see Example 7.25, pp. 229–230.

⁵⁰ Spiller 1971, p. 475; Klee BF/164, “1. Beide Farben rufen sich im Auge wechselseitig hervor. 2. zwischen beiden Farben steht grau.”

⁵¹ Boulez 2015, p. 87, “And thus we can also imagine a kind of music that, like the clouds in the sky,

does not truly develop but that only exists through changes in its appearance as such. That kind of music is not written to be heard from beginning to end. It could be a sound basis recorded on tape. This music can only be heard if it is activated [unchained as it were] by an instrument, like a piano, and if that piano reaches a certain dynamic threshold. If the piano is not playing very loud, or not a tall, the sound basis will vanish. I have taken this insight from the works of Klee.”

⁵² See O’Hagan 2017, pp. 274–275.

⁵³ Boulez 1989, p. 26, “Il n’a pas eu de Bach et de Mozart une vision servile, épigonale, il a analysé les méthodes, la pensée, les moyens d’écriture propres à ces compositeurs, d’où cette sorte de transsubstantiation qui fait toute l’originalité de sa démarche et lui donne sa rare validité. Même Kandinsky, pourtant proche de l’univers de Schönberg, n’est pas rattaché, avec une telle profondeur et une telle nécessité, à la pensée musicale.”

⁵⁴ On the different types of resonance in *Constellation*, see Hagan 2017, p. 223.

⁵⁵ Boulez 1987, pp. 93–113, p. 106, the description by Boulez himself. Regardless of whether it is assigned to one of the two categories, time is directional or non-directional, depending on the distribution of durations. However, while a static distribution in striped time tends to give the impression of smooth time, a differentiated directed distribution in smooth time is usually easily confused with that obtained from striped time, especially from adjacent values.

⁵⁶ My performance of *Constellation-Miroir of 3rd Sonate* by Boulez at my piano recital vol. 8 at Toppan Hall, Tokyo, in 2020, from 23:52: <https://youtu.be//IKn-TaGCn-8?si=HCZOW1KWi3giw6k3> (last accessed April 12, 2025). Another of my performances of the same work at my piano recital vol. 6 at the same Hall in 2018, <https://youtu.be/SkcYOH0E01Q?si=LeuYk0ik-f918RU> (last accessed April 12, 2025).

⁵⁷ See Boulez 1989, pp. 166, 168, “Ce qui, justement, me semble extraordinaire c’est que, dans des tableaux où le concept de mobilité ne viendrait pas à l’esprit, il y ait ce fond amorphe qui provoque la mobilité du regard et que sur ce fond soit greffée une morphologie qui appelle, au

contraire, la fixité du regard. C’est le seul exemple d’imagination picturale mentale de cette sorte que je connaisse.”

⁵⁸ For information on Boulez’s “work in progress,” see note 28.

⁵⁹ O’Hagan 2017, p. 186.

⁶⁰ My performance of *Trope of 3rd Sonate* by Boulez at my piano recital at Toppan Hall, Tokyo in 2020, from 18:19: <https://youtu.be//IKn-TaGCn-8?si=H-Mkge9I76YZvIQY> (last accessed April 12, 2025). Another of my performances of the same work at my piano recital at the same hall in 2018, <https://youtu.be/wchNaLKqSbM?si=lnKnTU4GJRjUy2eW> (last accessed April 12, 2025).

⁶¹ Boulez 1981, p. 162, “Quant à la conception générale ordonnant ces cinq formants, elle est basée sur une répartition symétrique et mobile autour du formant central Constellation (Constellation-Miroir). Le graphique ci-dessous montrera comment est réalisée cette répartition: autour du noyau central (lui-même groupement de cellules) gravitent les 4 formants groupés deux à deux sur des orbites concentriques, l’orbite extérieure pouvant devenir intérieure et réciproquement. Cela donne en tout seulement 8 possibilités d’exécution étant données les symétries auxquelles doivent obéir les permutations.” See *ibid.*, pp. 151–163.

⁶² See *ibid.*, pp. 158–159, and Boulez 2019, p. XX, “[...] the second formant, Trope, was originally printed in the form of a spiral-bound notebook, in accordance with the circular-form concept imagined by the composer, its subsequent republication in the form of separate sheets marks a regression to a more traditional presentation.”

⁶³ On the Antiphonie, see Boulez 2019, p. XX, “[...] In their present form, the different possibilities of performance of the different fragments of Antiphonie can be reduced to the four successive states through which the piece evolved in the course of its gestation: 1. Antiphonie / (1957); 2. Antiphonie / | (1958–59); 3. Sigle (1960); 4. TRAIT INITIAL/premier trait médian (1963– ...) [...]”

⁶⁴ See Boulez 1981, p. 386. Boulez mentioned about that in this discussion of comparison between *Pierrot lunaire* of Schoenberg and *Le Marteau sans maître* of Boulez. “Au contraire, j’ai tâché

d'imbriquer les trois cycles de telle sorte que la démarche au travers de l'œuvre en devienne plus complexe, usant de la réminiscence et des rapports virtuels; seule, la dernière pièce donne, en quelque sorte, la *solution*, la *clef*, de ce labyrinthe. Cette conception formelle m'a entraîné, d'ailleurs, beaucoup plus loin, en libérant totalement la forme d'une prédétermination; ici, le premier pas était franchi, par la rupture avec la forme 'unidirectionnelle.'

⁶⁵ Spiller 1961, p. 471. "We free our pendulum from gravity, we let it fly to the divine, dynamic realm, the realm of the spirit, of complete rotation and whole movement, the realm symbolised by the circle, where pure colours are truly at home." Klee BF/159.

⁶⁶ Klee 1964, no. 941, "Ingres is said to have ordered the motionless; I want to go beyond pathos and order motion. (The new Romanticism.)"

⁶⁷ O'Hagan 2017, p. 189 and p. 239, note 22, letter to Stockhausen, September 1957, Stockhausen Stiftung.

⁶⁸ Klee BG I.2/156, BG I.2/160-161, BG I.2/140, BF/183 etc.

⁶⁹ Boulez 1981, p. 157, "j'ai une prédilection marquée pour les grands 'ensembles,' centrés autour d'un faisceau de possibilités déterminées."

⁷⁰ Ibid., pp. 151-163.

⁷¹ Ibid., p. 157, "Il m'est de plus en plus étranger de concevoir des œuvres comme productions fragmentaires; j'ai une prédilection marquée pour les grands 'ensembles,' centrés autour d'un faisceau de possibilités déterminées. (Là, encore, l'influence de Joyce! ...) Aussi bien les cinq formants me laissent-ils sans doute le loisir d'engendrer d'autres 'développants,' s'imposant comme des tous distincts, se rattachant, toutefois, par leur structure, aux formants initiaux. Ce Livre constituerait un labyrinthe, une spirale dans le temps. Mais revenons aux cinq formants réels. Je les ai ainsi appelés par analogie avec l'acoustique. On sait qu'un timbre est rendu caractéristique par ses formants; j'estime que, de même, la physionomie d'une œuvre provient de ses formants structurels: caractères spécifiques généraux, susceptibles d'engendrer des développements. Chacun d'eux apparaît dans chaque pièce, exclusivement, afin

de pouvoir, plus tard, constituer ces 'développants,' que j'ai mentionnés, par échange, interférence, interaction, destruction. Le nom donné à ces formants cerne leur physionomie, met l'accent sur leurs caractéristiques individuelles."

- ⁷² O'Hagan 2017, p. 186, and p. 237, note 9, "Et la forme est en évolution constante avec des zones floues entre des zones homogènes." Letter postmarked April 1, 1956, Stockhausen Stiftung.
- ⁷³ Spiller 1961, p. 9, Klee BG I.1/17.
- ⁷⁴ Klee 1964, p. 374, no. 1081, Diary IV, "Polyphonic painting is superior to music in that, here, the time element becomes a spatial element. The notion of simultaneity stands out even more richly."
- ⁷⁵ "Sonata 3 (BWV 1016)," written by J. F. Agricola, in Bach Digital [9-12], bach-digital.de/rsc/viewer/BachDigitalSource.derivate.00085121/Image020.jpg (last accessed April 12, 2025).
- ⁷⁶ On the meaning of the neighbour tone, see the diagram: [Neighboring tone](#). (last accessed April 12, 2025). "Neighbor tones move away from a note by step then return to the note." It is a movement that stitches a certain note with a neighboring note to form a mountain shape, that is, it goes and comes back. When I describe in the article that the theme of the fourth part of the first movement of No. 3 BWV 1016 is "a sound pattern that undulates like a fine zigzag wave made of neighbour tones of 16th notes," I am referring to the movement of the e-dis-e pattern of the 2nd, 3rd and 4th notes within each of the four grouping of 16th notes, "♪ x-e-dis-e," "fis-e-dis-e," "gis-e-dis-e."
- ⁷⁷ I'll try to explain this meaning in a little more detail. Let's take up the three-note patterns of the elegant triplets in the second part, which are grouped in threes, i. e. 1-2-3, 1-2-3, 1-2-3; "♪ h-fis-e," "fis-dis-cis," and "dis-h-ais." If we try to create a new grouping by shifting each note by one, as the Klees write, 2-3-1, 2-3-1, 2-3-1, then the new groupings of "♪ fis-e-fis," "dis-cis-dis," and "h-ais-h" will be emphasized and stand out. As you can see from the explanation of "neighbour tones" in the previous note, this is the same as the "a sound pattern that undulates like a fine zigzag wave made of neighbour tones of 16th notes" in

the thema of the first part! Here, I speculate on the true intentions of the Klees, who went to such lengths to achieve this effect.

⁷⁸ On September 25, 2024, this was performed at a closed lecture concert entitled “The Complete Works for Violin and Harpsichord BWV 1014–1019 by J. S. Bach” hosted by the Classical Music (Music Lovers) Association in Tachikawa, Tokyo. Vn. Chiharu Taki, pf. Yumiko Segawa.

⁷⁹ Klee 1964, p. 394, no. 1124.

⁸⁰ Klee 1964, p. 384. The date in Klee’s diary referred to above is June 28, 1918, but Klee had been staying in Gersthofen since January 3 of the same year for military service, apart from his family.

⁸¹ Boulez 2015, p. 65 (Boulez 1989, pp. 65–72).

⁸² Please listen to Debussy’s *La Mer* (with score), <https://youtu.be/KUFpcPEcwTo?si=U8yb5Kogkm1548x-> (last accessed April 12, 2025).

⁸³ Boulez 2015, p. 65 (Boulez 1989, p. 72), “Debussy, for instance, created harmonic patterns that are repeated at a fixed pace, patterns with double sharps, others with triplets, meaning that they are somewhat slower. These two patterns, that we could refer to as ‘spacio-temporal’—they are related to time and at the same time they are audible or acoustic objects in space—are superimposed.”

⁸⁴ Klee 1964, p. 374, no. 1081, Diary IV.

⁸⁵ Boulez 2015, pp. 70–71 (Boulez 1989, pp. 72–75).

⁸⁶ Spiller 1961, p. 285, Klee BF/54, see fig. 21, “Since music without dynamics sounds mechanical and expressionless, I select qualitative representation C and give the line more or less weight according to the tone quality, while the quantitative representation in B expresses itself in the vertical lines for bars and parts of bars.” See also fig. 22 in “Form einer Beilage.”

⁸⁷ Spiller 1961, p. 285, Klee BF/54, see fig. 21, “C.”

⁸⁸ See List of Works by Takeo Hoshiya, <https://tokinokatachi.com/hoshiya.html> (last accessed April 12, 2025).

⁸⁹ My performance of *Four Seasons for Piano* by Takeo Hoshiya, <https://youtu.be/-GW2sPjt3eY?si=JWiF2QGpSpHxYC8x> (last accessed April 12, 2025).

⁹⁰ Yumiko Segawa’s Piano Recital vol. 10, “‘P. Boulez: Second sonata’ in another operation, 2

in 1 in 2 -part 2-, ‘Pflanzlich-seltsam (by Paul Klee): to B individual, fraying, emergence’” held on January 27, 2024, at Toppan Hall (Tokyo, Japan). Program: Louis Couperin, *Prélude à l’imitation de Mr. Froberger*, a-moll; I. Xenakis, *Mists*; B. Bartók, *Im Freien*, Sz. 81; J. S. Bach, *Englische Suite Nr. 3*, g-moll BWV808; A. Schönberg, *Drei Klavierstücke*, op. 11, Nr. 3 *Bewegte*; Takeo Hoshiya, *Four Seasons for Piano*; P. Boulez, *Deuxième Sonate pour Piano*.

⁹¹ Hoshiya 2017, see N-4, and score.

⁹² *Ibid.*, N-4, “Notes on Score 1. Pitch [the pitch is indicated by a rectangular note on the staff] 4. Dynamics. In addition, very thin lines in [...] these notes should always be strongly noticeable from the surrounding dynamic level and played as briefly as possible.”

⁹³ Klee BF/40, “Ausgeschaltet wird das Abwägen erst, wo die Diagonale aufhört, wo die Wage erstarret, z. B. bei diesem allerprimitivsten Rhythmus des Structuralen, wo es nur horizontale oder nur verticale Linien gibt.”

⁹⁴ *Ibid.*, “Denn ein Ohnmächtiger fällt unter Umständen doch vom Stuhl. Dieser Rest schwindet erst ganz in der liegenden Stellung. Der Mensch wird zum Baustein.”

⁹⁵ *Ibid.*, “Horizontale auf Kosten der Verticalen. Es tritt eine beträchtliche Entspannung ein, ein episches Tempo gegenüber der Dramatik des Vertikalcharakters, was natürlich ein Abwägen nach hüben und drüben nicht ausschaltet. Die Verticale ist immer noch da!”

⁹⁶ Boulez 2015, p. 88, “Grohmann shows exactly how Klee creates coloured Lengths of varying widths as a basis for these works, which he painted after a trip to Egypt. Here and there they run from one side to the other. They are cut off by verticals or diagonals, depending on the shape that is created, in such a way that the horizontal structure on the canvas is to a certain extent neutralised by the vertical one. There is another system of lengths, which are much bigger and which have different colours. Its design seems to express nothing more than the structure it reveals. The structure takes the form of the architecture of a landscape. I was able to see these aquarelles quite recently at the occasion of the exposition *Paul Klee and Music*, shown in 1985 at the Musée de l’Art Moderne. Ole

Hendrik Moe, who arranged the exhibition, draws a parallel with music in his discussion of the works. His view is that some paintings with stripe patterns unmistakably evoke the same differentiation that sounds do, because they are split in two. In that way a rhythmical or flexible motive is created.” Cf. Boulez 1989, pp. 172–173.

⁹⁷See Klee BF/29-43 etc.

⁹⁸Boulez 2015, p. 74, “But in these scores that had something positive to offer for the eye, auditory aspects had been totally neglected. The outcomes prove that the connection between what can be seen and what can be heard must be founded on a more stable basis.” Cf. Boulez 1989, p. 100.

⁹⁹Boulez 2015, p. 58 (Boulez 1989, pp. 8–9).

¹⁰⁰The titles of my Klee-recitals and Klee-albums are as follows: Yumiko Segawa Piano Recital at Toppan Hall (Tokyo); Vol. 5, “On the Border of a Fertile Country (by Klee)”—line-polyphony ⇒...!?!—in 2016 (CD of the same title); Vol. 6, “Insula Dulcamara (by Klee)”—how is the time bubble? d → d—in 2018; Vol. 7, “A Garden for Orpheus (by Klee)”—line-in the thickness of this world—in 2019; CD of vol. 6 & 7, “Anatomy of Aphrodite (by Klee)”—cutting, disassembling, reconstitution—; Vol. 8, “Composition with windows (by Klee)~B’”—notation ⇔ sonate ⇔ bagatelle—in 2020 (CD of the same title); CD “Stadt Ende (by Klee)”—the play between brilliance and brilliance ⇔ the brilliance between play and play.

¹⁰¹My 2025 performance related to Paul Klee will be as follows: A solo piano concert including a program of works such as Boulez’s *Constellation* at the museum concert for the Paul Klee exhibition *Solitude and Solidarity* to be held at the Shizuoka City Museum of Art on June 29, 2025. I am also performing a solo piano concert, the series of Yumiko Segawa Piano Recital (Klee-recital) Vol. 11, “Beginning of a poem (by Klee)”—from Sonate to Incises—including a program of *Constellation, Incises, Notations, Sonate No. 1, Une page d’éphéméride*, and *Fragment d’une Ébauche* etc. by Boulez at Toppan Hall, Tokyo, on December 6, 2025.

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